

CHANGING TRENDS OF HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY: EMERGENCE OF MILLENNIALS AND GEN Z AS FUTURE CUSTOMERS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

In today's global scenario world is witnessing major changes on various fronts. Even Hospitality industry is influenced by this. As hospitality industry is extremely competitive it is necessary for the hoteliers to keep a track of these changes and trends which are happening in this industry. One of the ways to ensure the success of the hospitality industry is to forecast the needs of new generations of guests and travelers, also it is inevitable that the future belongs to new generation such as the millennials and Gen Z and so the hoteliers must be aware of their tastes, likes & dislikes because they are going to be the future of the hospitality industry. This paper tries to analyze the trends and needs pertaining to the millennials and Gen Z from the hospitality industry's perspective as they are likely to be the major portion of hotels future customers and they also possess more power to influence any other generations ever.

Keywords: Millennial, Gen Z, Tech Savvy, Hospitality Industry.

Introduction

In the last two decades, lot of attention was given to the Baby Boomer generation by the hotel industry. But lately the hospitality industry has become a niche market for millennial and generation Z thereby creating a challenges to the hotels related to service quality. The future belongs to Gen Z though the present generations are Millennial, and these generations are more aware and well informed about their primarily need and wants. They normally like to have things to be basic and simple without much complication. This generation being driven by the technology like speed and anticipate things to be fast and without any fuss when it comes to product and services. Also they would like to have advanced technology without any compromise. Lot of hotels today are creating customized services as per the needs of the Millennia's. Millennial like experiences than the product for which they would like to spend money on and In order to break the monotony Hoteliers must bring about novel ideas to there are services, also considering the current scenario sales and marketing strategies of hotels must shift from traditional 'targeted' customers to millennial and the Gen Z, which is a larger demographic. Those who were born after 1996 are called as Gen Z and they belong to about 32% of the total global population of the world and this is expected to be 7.7 billion by the end of the year

2020. Millennial are those who were born after 1995, they are around 31.5% 32% of the total global population. India has the world's largest youth population with 356 million people in the age group of 10-25 years as per the 2014 United Nations report also by 2020, India has become the world's youngest country with 64% of its population in the working age group. Millennial are those people who were young adolescents in the year 2000 while Generation Z are the ones who are born in or after 2000, the oldest of whom would currently be about 18-20 years of age.

Gen Z have grown up in a world which has been dominated with innovative technology. Most of them have born after the invention of Google and Smartphone; this generation think in 4D, wear watches not to tell time, but to experience feeling of holding a paper map in their hands. Gen Z is constantly connected, with 41% of them spend on an average more than 3 hours a day on computers for non-college related activities they prefer to use 5 screens at one time for multi-tasking, They are continuously on social networks considering this to be their social life. Gen Z likes apps with privacy, such as Snapchat, vine and Instagram. Facebook is not that popular with this group, as quarter of them have left Facebook in 2014.

It is believed that 73% of this generation gets connected to the Internet within an hour of waking up. Gen Z belongs to do it yourself (DIY) culture. They are continuously witnessing the technology become obsolete, for example DVDs, answering machines, game consoles. They are also known to be independent learner and self-educators, and are comfortable to learn things via YouTube or Google. They lack patience, and like visuals to text, they communicate through emoji. This generation are constantly worried about missing out on things, a term dubbed "FOMO" (fear of missing out), this is the reason that today's hoteliers should connect with these generations, try to understand their technology needs and habits as major hotels business will come from them. Today we all talk about disruption, considering this vital point hotels should increase technology features in their rooms such as extra electrical outlets, strong Wi-Fi connectivity, mobile device charging ports and self-service tablets, digital booking, check-in and check-out via smartphones and dial-inns inside rooms.

In order to remain competitive current hoteliers must thrive upon the emerging novel trends in order to stop to disappoint the guests and be ahead of their competitors. Hotel must work very hard on improving on guest satisfaction as 76% of millennial's spend their own experiences rather than things.

Now a days there is a tendency to mix business with leisure this is becoming very evident on Domestic as well as international stage. As per a survey around 55% millennial like to extend business trips in order to have extra leisure time. Hotels located near malls and tourist places, have come up with special weekend packages, consisting of brunch served at the poolside for transportation services to visit shopping areas.

This generation of international travelers rely on ratings of reviews for making booking internationally. Hotels must manage their online reputation for all reviews. This new generation have come out with a new concept 'Bleisure which deals with work, business and leisure together and so hotels are planning services and facilities to meet both this requirements at the same time example of this

can be staycation packages which are specially designed for millennial's different activities are planned for rejuvenating the guest and altering their hectic schedule such as workshops on art, spa Shine signature massage for weekend, camp on fitness boot, parrot watching long brunch spread and Feast etc.

Objective of the study

- To study how Millennial's and Gen Z are influencing the Hospitality Industry
- To study and understand how hospitality industry is catering to the needs of Millennial's and Gen Z

Methods

For this study data was collected through secondary sources like books, journals, Websites and Research Articles.

Literature Review

As per Stephan (2018), when evaluating hotel service, millennials are not just looking for white-linen service and bellboys to carry their luggage up to their room or a concierge but when they enter a hotel, they want to feel completely at home, connected and be part of an experience (Mhlanga and Tichaawa, 2016). As per Woods and King (2010) Gen Z requires a digital experience which has a direct impact on their engagement and satisfaction. Mobile technology is what today's generation thrive on to interact as per. According to Kovaleski (2008) social media plays a key role in how this generation evaluates hotel experiences because they are online customers, and the masters of social media their demand of a hotel experience should be tailored to their needs because throughout the world hotel referrals are made via social connections, this has made the hotels to offer the best possible experience to this generation guests.

As per (Dimitriou and Blum, 2015) technology is key for hotels to win millennial loyalty. Watkins (2015) says that with digital experience, millennial's do like eco-friendly hotels and its practices to become part of their hotel experiences. As per (Dimitriou and Blum, 2015) green practices and environmentally friendly programs followed by hotels are preferred by Millennial's concept such green washing green washing practices, helps in

gaining the trust of millennial. Woods and King (2010) states that the millennial generation is obsessed with the speed, during the process of check in and check out of a hotel, millennial are often found to be much less patient than previous generations. Millennials and Gen Z like a hotel lobby where they can sit and drink coffee surrounded by other people, rather than having a coffee machine being installed in their room as per (Stephan, 2018).

Current trends pertaining to Generation Z and Millennials

Millennials are always on a look out for experiences rather than a product itself and they are always looking to break monotony of work-life so they expect this through the experience that they gain while staying in the hotel. Many International hotel brands today are specially designing and renovating their properties to cater to this fast paced, young travelers.

1. To attract these generations many hotels today are renovating their lobbies, rooms and interiors through the addition of bright, vibrant colors.
2. The new trend adopted by many international hotels today is the installation of pool table for guests in the lobby, this is accompanied with buzzing bar playing karaoke sessions, musical program and live band which also encourages young and upcoming musicians and musical bands to perform on weekends Gen Z and Millennia's are very fond of these young performers.
3. Since the Millennials work very hard during the working days, and relax and travel and do excursion and explore new many hotels are coming up with weekend and vacation packages for them.
4. Some International brands of hotels are introducing novel high energy vibe party on the poolside with the arrangement of dining options for these young, travelers.
5. If today's Hoteliers need positive promotion on social media channels
6. and good business they will continuously have to delight these young generation by implementation of quick and speedy check-ins check-outs along with gourmet, F&B

dining experiences that to at affordable prices so that in return these, satisfied millennia's and gen Z will actively and positively promote their businesses

Eco-friendly Practices

Gen Z is still in a growing economic force, but one thing is very profound about this generation that is this generation is very much aware of environmental issues and its effects and so they more concerned about the ecological balance. Most of these guests are looking for sustainable authentic experiences. The hospitality industry, in order to attract these guests, has to adopt practices which will meet the expectations of these generations. As a part of best environmental practices hotel chains are replacing the plastic items with biodegradable products nowadays many hotels have completely replaced plastic with paper alternatives. The management of many reputed chain of luxury hotels have already started using Green Solutions which are designed for energy, water and waste reduction, at the same time also improve and lessen its impact on the environment, today's young generation are very sensitive towards the environmental issues they participate.

Many International chains of luxury hotels are discouraging use plastic items at the hotel and have replaced them with alternate wherever possible. Use of plastics has been completely avoided Today's generation participates in these environment friendly practices which consists of reusing of guests towels in order to conserve water, also not to use plastic bottles, straws and plastics items.

Technology Advancement

Today's young generation is already tech savvy so they prefer to use advanced technology. Star hotels have started to implement advanced technology already, even AI are being installed to execute various tasks in the hotels, even to make the check in and out procedure fast I Pads are seen and used at reception desk, also in the hotel rooms tabs are being used for the guests for adjusting the light, to order food, and to watch TV, even the Food 8 Beverage will be on on-screen menu. Millennials and Generation Z have been very prevalence on Facebook, Instagram, and

Snapchat, this probably is the reason that they are more connected with the world in comparison to the older generations, and so the Millennials consider travel as their birthright as per the research 68% of them give travel they also share their photos in-person experience of the destination and on social media, such is the influence of Social media that around 84% of the Facebook users said that their friends' posts have influenced them to make their future travel plans.

Expectation of Millennial and Gen Z from hotels

Gen Z are born in the era of internet, smartphones, and on demand content, their expectations from the hotels is to offer them same technology and services at the time of check-in and out they prefer mobile check-in and keyless entry in to their rooms, they expect to be entertained with services such as Netflix, Hulu, YouTube, in their room TV they also prefer using messaging apps to order and communicate.

The expectation of Gen Z from the hotels would be to get digital in-room assistants when they check in the hotel at the same time they would expect everything to be instantly available to them since they are digital natives so the hotels need to rethink about their product and services and make changes as per the behavior, habits and traits of Gen Z, since this breed of generation are prone towards sustainable food choices and their shift is towards healthier and organic foods

The young generations of great chefs and food & Beverage servers also have different ideas related to food. Hotel industry should consider the next few generations as the industry's greatest assets, and so there will be continuous challenge to the hoteliers related to F&B because Generation Z have already began to show their social and economic presence throughout the globe.

Millennial and Gen Z are those who are in the range of age between 18 to 34 they are expected to represent 50% of travelers by 2025, hospitality industry needs to define their

strategies based on their demographics, personality traits and habits, these generation travel a lot, are early adopters of technology they like personalized interactions and are spontaneous. The majority of Millennials today are self-sufficient, tech-savvy travelers who are comfortable using apps or mobile websites. Hotels need to make sure that their offerings are up to date and user-friendly. At business meetings and conferences, these generations expect hotels and conference centers to have high quality tech equipment and a knowledgeable support staff. While past generations relied on travel agents, today these generations use the Internet to do their research. Millennials are well researched when it comes to travel whether it's lodgings, activities, or loyalty programs. These sites not only enable users to find the best deals on flights and hotels but offer browsers social proof for each destination. Millennials and Gen Z rely on their peer's online testimonials to guide their purchasing decisions 92% of travelers trust reviews and make informed decision based on their online research.

Millennials and Generation Z are more likely to pick a travel destination and activities based on what their peers share online over branded travel ads. As a result, Millennials and Gen Z have made an indelible mark on the travel and tourism marketing industry and have transformed what is means to be successful in marketing in travel and tourism. Millennials and Gen Z not only use social media for inspiration and research, they also use it to share their own travel experiences. These places or activities are focused on the kinds of content that Millennials are most likely to share such as adventure activities and excursions, restaurants, and the outdoors. One of the biggest changes is that for today's travelers, social media and sharing has become part of the guest experience. Travelers share photos and reviews both before and during their travels not just after all these new technologies act as successful marketing tools for the hospitality Industry.

organizations for local cuisine, recreational opportunities, and cultural events .

6. **Friendly food strategy:** Since Millennials and Gen Z are ready to pay they should be provided with local, authentic food, at the same time options of sandwiches, pizzas, pastas, desserts and cold bakery should be made available at the hotel lounge during the peak hours of the hotel.
7. **Social media savvy:** As it is evident that almost 97 percent of Millennials post their travel and hotel experiences on social media this creates a huge impact for this they commonly this is because of the explosion of social media over the last decade therefore what type of content being shared on social media plays a very important role on the minds of the audiences

Conclusion

The future hoteliers need to implement ecofriendly practices and waste disposal in their hotels as these new generations are very conscious about environmental issues, also food & beverage options must be as per the liking of millennial and Gen Z ,a lot of attention on technology, amenities and entertainment must be provided to this generation of guests. Hospitality Industry should take advantage of their FOMO through social media, they should be able to convince them that they are going to miss out on lot of things if they don't visit your hotel this can create a lot of impact on the business of the hotel. To appeal Generation Z and Millennials alike, hoteliers also need to have an online presence which is supported by social proof, brand ambassadors, and user generated content.

It's no longer enough to have free internet in your properties. Offerings now need to extend to seamless Wi-Fi for multiple devices, hiccup-free video streaming, and Internet functionality that integrates with hotel systems such as mobile check-in and room access, bill payment, and even ordering capabilities. With Gen Z being always online and completely comfortable with social media, it's vital for hotel to have strong, active presences on social media that guests can connect with at any time like up-to-date profiles, frequent postings, interactive communication on multiple channels, and a solid social marketing strategy. Hoteliers need to come out of their comfort zone and plan for more creativity in food and beverage options also making it more organic, healthier through sustainable and responsible manner. The management of the hotels must work on the principle of 'what's next' if they intend to stay ahead in this competition, they have to continuously work on how to attract and retain these younger generation.

Practical Implication of this Study

Millennials and Gen Z are the largest living generation today, hospitality industry must gear up and be ready to cater to their needs this study will help the hoteliers to know the trends, likes, and dislikes preferences and requirements of this generation, and identify factors influencing hotel experiences for millennial tourists this will also help the hoteliers to welcome them and keep the hotels portfolio up-to-date in order to turn them into loyal customers of future, the findings of this study could help hotels to understand the nuances of this niche market and be prepared to offer a hotel experience that meets their expectations

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